

Implementation of the Market Day Program in Contextual Numeracy Learning for Phase B Elementary School Students

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Article Information	ABSTRACT
Received: XX.XX.XXXX	<i>Background:</i> The purpose of this study was to examine how the Market Day program was used by Phase B elementary school students to improve their contextual numeracy skills. This research primarily focused on changing the way they traded, with students given play money as capital that they had to spend in full. This study was conducted qualitatively and descriptively, utilizing participant observation and document analysis of students' calculation writing. The results demonstrated that the difficulty of spending money appropriately forced students to engage in complex cognitive processes such as complex problem solving, value estimation, and mixed arithmetic operations. The use of scraps of paper as a recording tool provided clear evidence of the development of students' mathematical thinking. This program not only improved students' numeracy skills but also fostered a careful personality in basic financial management.
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INTRODUCTION

Basic education in Indonesia is currently undergoing a transformation through the Merdeka Curriculum, which provides ample space for the development of literacy and numeracy (Sofiroh et al., 2025). Numeracy is not merely the ability to perform mechanical calculations; it is the ability of students to use mathematics to solve everyday problems (Purwoko, 2025). Understanding the concept of numeracy is very important for developing more complex thinking logic in elementary school, especially for Phase B students in grades 3 and 4 (Witono et al., 2025).

Learning is a system of interaction between students and teachers that occurs during learning activities. In this process, teachers not only deliver lessons but also motivate students (Putra & Kristrifena, 2024). Numeracy learning, especially in Phase B, plays a very important role in laying the foundation for students' cognitive and logical abilities (Tauhid, Safari, et al., 2024). According to et al. (Aulia et al., 2025), numeracy learning is a process designed to create an environment that enables students to engage in mathematical learning activities. According to Siswanto (Siswanto et al., 2024), numeracy learning is a systematic field of study that investigates the art, language, relationships, and patterns of thinking that help humans master and understand natural, social, and economic issues. Meanwhile, according to Hayati and Jannah (Hayati & Jannah, 2024), numeracy learning is a field of science that studies numbers and patterns of structure, change, and space. Based on these definitions, it can be synthesized that numeracy learning is a systematic process that enables students to explore numbers patterns, and spatial structures

to develop logical thinking patterns for solving economic, natural, and social problems.

At this point, it is expected that students will not only have mechanical counting skills but also numeracy skills, which means they can apply mathematical concepts to solve everyday problems (Sappaile et al., 2023). However, the reality in the field shows that many students experience an inconsistent relationship between the theory learned in class and the situation outside of class (Engelbrecht & Borba, 2024). Mathematics is often considered a complicated subject that only uses conceptual symbols on paper (Heila, 2025). This causes problems in numeracy learning, resulting in students experiencing difficulties in learning mathematics (Ananda & Wandini, 2022). Therefore, learning that only focuses on textbooks tends to fail to build a "sense of number" in students, so innovations are needed that can bring real-life situations into the school environment.

With advances in technology, especially in the field of education, teachers must be able to utilize various types of technology to help students learn (Putra & Kristrifena, 2024). The Merdeka Curriculum allows teachers to innovate with project-based learning that combines various skills (Brahmandika, 2024). One example is the Market Day activity, which is designed thematically (Ningrum & Nugroho, 2024).

Studies have shown that student participation in practical activities greatly influences their mathematical abilities. Research by (Hidayat et al., 2025) shows that entrepreneurship-based learning models such as Market Day are effective in improving understanding of social mathematics concepts and providing higher learning motivation compared to conventional methods. Similarly, a study conducted by (Hayati & Jannah, 2024) reveals that contextual learning using

buying and selling simulations can significantly develop elementary school students' estimation and logical reasoning skills. Furthermore, the results of a study and Rahmawati (Sayekti & Rahmawati, 2025) emphasize that Market Day not only teaches students to count, but also teaches them to be more independent and work together. This study shows that a learning environment similar to social reality greatly helps students maintain their understanding of logic and mathematical numbers.

The Market Day Program at SD Negeri I Bana Based on the success of these studies, SD Negeri I Bana implemented the Market Day program as a strategic solution. This program is a project-based learning model that simulates market activities. In this study, the Market Day program was specifically modified to become a fun and challenging field of numeracy. By introducing a random capital coupon system with play money, teachers created different problem stories for each student. This encouraged students to think critically because they could not simply follow their friends' choices; each student had a different numerical "mission" based on the amount of money they had.

This study focuses primarily on how Phase B students can be motivated to use counting techniques, price estimation, and logical decision-making within budget constraints. This simulation helps students understand that every economic activity has mathematical consequences that must be taken into account, which are then recorded in the form of total expenditure calculations. Through this approach, numeracy is no longer seen as an academic burden, but rather as a meaningful and essential life skill.

METHOD

This study used a qualitative approach with a descriptive research design, which aimed to describe in depth the implementation of the Market Day Program as contextual numeracy learning for Phase B elementary school students. The study was conducted at SD Negeri I Bana, Klaten Regency, with 20 Phase B students who were directly involved in Market Day activities as research subjects.

Data collection was conducted through participatory observation, in which researchers were directly involved in Market Day activities to observe students' numeracy activities during the buying and selling process. The observation focused on students' ability to perform arithmetic operations, estimate prices, record transactions, and make decisions based on budget constraints. The observation was conducted based on Phase B numeracy indicators that refer to the Merdeka Curriculum Learning Outcomes.

In addition to observation, the data was reinforced through document analysis, in the form of students' calculations on transaction sheets used during Market Day activities. These documents were analyzed to examine students' numerical thinking processes, including the accuracy

of their calculations, their calculation strategies, and how they adjusted their spending to their available capital.

Data analysis was conducted using qualitative descriptive analysis techniques through three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Data validity was maintained through increased diligence, by conducting careful and repeated observations during the activity and comparing the observation results with the documentation data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Market Day as Contextual Numeracy Learning

The implementation of the Market Day Program at SD Negeri I Klaten Bana shows that numeracy learning can take place contextually and closely relate to the daily lives of Phase B students. The buying and selling activities, which were designed to resemble real-life situations, provided space for students to interact directly with numeracy problems, such as reading price lists, calculating total purchases, and adjusting expenses to a predetermined budget (Theresia et al., 2022). This condition shows that numeracy is not only learned as an abstract concept, but is applied in a context that is meaningful to students (Amalia et al., 2025). Numeracy learning through Market Day strengthens students' understanding of the use of mathematical concepts in everyday life (Wayan et al., 2024). Activities that involve direct experience help students build connections between numeracy knowledge and real-life situations, making the learning process more relevant and easier to understand (Rahmadani et al., 2022).

B. Counting Activities in the Buying and Selling Process

During Market Day activities, students demonstrated their ability to apply number concepts and simple arithmetic operations. Students were involved in activities such as calculating the price of goods, adding up the total purchase, and comparing the value of the money they had with the price of the goods they chose. The use of play money as a medium of transaction helped students recognize nominal values and perform calculations concretely (Setiyadi et al., 2022). Some students still needed more time to perform calculations. This condition reflects the normal stage of numeracy development in Phase B (Tauhid, Syafawani, et al., 2024). The process of recalculating and correcting mistakes became part of the learning process, so that students gained meaningful learning experiences through real activities (Hidayat et al., 2025).

C. Decision Making Based on Numeracy Calculations

Students' decision-making skills are evident when they adjust their shopping choices to the predetermined budget. Students compare prices between items and change their choices when the total purchase exceeds their budget. This process demonstrates the use of calculation results as a basis for decision making (Siswanto et al., 2024). Through Market Day activities, students not only practice arithmetic, but also learn to use numeracy as a problem-solving tool (Aulia et al., 2025). This experience supports the development of logical

and rational thinking skills in the context of everyday life (Saputra, 2024).

D. Student Communication and Attitudes Towards Numeracy

Aspects of communication and numeracy attitudes were also evident during Market Day. Students were able to convey their calculations to their friends and explain the reasons for choosing items based on the available budget. Confidence in transactions and accuracy in calculating the remaining money showed a positive attitude towards numeracy (Murtiningsih, 2022). Contextual numeracy learning helped students feel closer to mathematics (Yolanda et al., 2024). Learning situations that resembled real activities encouraged students to be more confident in using their calculation skills and to participate actively in the learning process (Utami, 2024).

CONCLUSION

The Market Day program at SD Negeri I Bana shows that contextual numeracy learning through buying and selling simulations improves the cognitive abilities and logical thinking of Phase B students. Students are motivated to perform complex cognitive processes such as mixed calculations, value estimation, and problem solving caused by budget constraints. The results of this study indicate that this project-based method not only transforms mathematics from abstract ideas into useful skills in everyday life, but also successfully fosters students' independence, perseverance, and confidence in basic financial management.

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REFERENCES

- Amalia, A., Suriasyah, A., Mulya, A., & Harsono, B. (2025). *Implementasi Program Market Day terhadap Kepemimpinan Siswa Sekolah Dasar*. 2009, 1424–1433.
- Ananda, E. R., & Wandini, R. R. (2022). Analisis perspektif guru dalam mengatasi kesulitan belajar siswa pada pembelajaran matematika sekolah dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(3), 4173–4181.
- Aulia, D., Khotami, E. N., & Arum, P. S. (2025). *PROGRAM MARKET DAY SEKOLAH DASAR IMPLEMENTATION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION THROUGH MARKET DAY PROGRAM ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS*. 6, 90–98.
- Brahmandika, S. (2024). Pengembangan strategi pembelajaran inovatif berbasis proyek Kurikulum Merdeka. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Dasar*, 9.
- Engelbrecht, J., & Borba, M. C. (2024). Recent developments in using digital technology in mathematics education. *ZDM – Mathematics Education*, 56(2), 281–292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-023-01530-2>
- Hayati, M., & Jannah, M. (2024). Pentingnya kemampuan literasi matematika dalam pembelajaran matematika. 4, 40–54.
- Helia, S. R., *Seminar Nasional Matematika Ilmu*, & Universitas Muhammadiyah Sukabumi. (2025). Upaya meningkatkan pemahaman konseptual bangun ruang sisi datar melalui integrasi teknologi dalam pembelajaran matematika kelas VIII SMP. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Matematika Ilmu*, 1, 49–62.
- Hidayat, R., Muchtar, Y., Alrizqi, D. G., & Reski, A. (2025). *Pemberdayaan Siswa Sekolah Dasar melalui Kegiatan Market Day untuk Membangun Kreativitas dan Kemandirian Berwirausaha*. 5(2).
- Murtiningsih, D. H. (2022). *Analisis Minat Belajar Peserta Didik Terhadap Pembelajaran Matematika di Sekolah Dasar*. 271–279.
- Ningrum, P., & Nugroho. (2024). Manajemen program market day di sekolah dasar. *Equity in Education Journal*, 6, 1–7.
- Purwoko, R. Y. (2025). *Pembelajaran mendalam berorientasi pada kemampuan numerasi siswa sekolah dasar*. 13–26.
- Putra, A. M., & Kristrifena. (2024). Efektivitas penerapan PPT interaktif dalam meningkatkan kemampuan pemecahan masalah pada pembelajaran matematika pembagian fase B. *Jurnal Ilmiah PGSD FKIP Universitas Mandiri*, 10, 1398–1406.
- Rahmadani, A., Wandini, R. R., Dewi, A., Zairima, E., & Putri, T. D. (2022). *Upaya Meningkatkan Berpikir Kritis dan Mengefektifkan Pendekatan Kontekstual dalam Pembelajaran Matematika Efforts to Improve Critical Thinking and Effective Contextual Approaches in Mathematics Learning*. 2(1), 427–433.
- Sappaile, B. I., Nugroho, A., Putro, S., & Ahmad, S. N. (2023). *Implementasi Model Pembelajaran Berbasis Proyek Dalam Penanaman Konsep Matematika pada Siswa Sekolah Menengah Program Studi Administrasi Rumah Sakit, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan Pelita Ibu*. 3, 8547–8557.
- Saputra, H. (2024). *Perkembangan Berpikir Matematis Pada Anak Usia Sekolah Dasar*. 6(2), 53–64.
- Sayekti, P. I., & Rahmawati, L. E. (2025). *Penerapan Literasi Finansial pada Siswa Sekolah Dasar dan Dampaknya terhadap Keterampilan Berwirausaha*. 14(3), 5677–5690.
- Setiyadi, D., Aviari, B. A., & Berliana, E. (2022). *Uang Koin dan Kertas Mainan Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Matematika Kontekstual pada Sekolah Dasar Toy Coin and Money as Contextual Mathematics Learning Media in Elementary Schools*. 3(September), 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.30595/jrpd.v3i2.12853>
- Siswanto, A., Sumarno, S., Reffiane, F., & Utami, S. (2024). *Menumbuhkan Jiwa Berwirausaha Siswa melalui Implementasi Proyek Market Day*. 5, 504–511.
- Sofiroh, M., Brebes, U. M., & Info, A. (2025). *Transformasi Pembelajaran Abad Ke-21 Di Sekolah Dasar: Integrasi Literasi Digital Dalam Kurikulum Merdeka*. 3(2), 102–111.
- Tauhid, K., Safari, Y., & Nurhida, P. (2024). *Karimah Tauhid, Volume 3 Nomor 9 (2024), e-ISSN 2963-590X*. 3, 9817–9824.
- Tauhid, K., Syafawani, U. R., Safari, Y., Piaget, M. J., Matematika, P., & Dasar, S. (2024). *TEORI PERKEMBANGAN BELAJAR PSIKOLOGIS KOGNITIF JEAN PIAGET: IMPLEMENTASI DALAM PEMBELAJARAN*. 3, 1488–1502.
- Theresia, D., Sami, S., Purnomo, S., Guru, P., & Dasar, S. (2022). *IMPLEMENTASI MARKET DAY UNTUK MENINGKATKAN NUMERASI DAN*. 3(1).

- Utami, N. D. (2024). *Penerapan Pendekatan Kontekstual untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Siswa Sekolah Dasar*. 2, 1–9.
- Wayan, N., Dewi, R., Luh, N., & Windayani, I. (2024). *Membangun Jiwa Enterpreneurship dan Kreativitas di Sekolah Melalui Kegiatan Market Day Berorientasi Kearifan Lokal*. 7, 100–112.
- Witono, S., Hadi, M. S., Jakarta, M., Info, A., & History, A. (2025). *Numerasi dan Kemampuan Berpikir Kreatif pada Pembelajaran Matematika di Sekolah Dasar*. 8, 2489–2496.
- Yolanda, A., Sihotang, M., Zebua, J. A., & Hutasoit, M. (2024).

Strategi Pembelajaran Kontekstual untuk Meningkatkan Pemahaman Konsep Siswa Sekolah Dasar. 2(3).